

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-4, AUGUST 2025

Editor-In-Chief: **Dr. Vishwanath Bite**
Managing Editor: **Dr. Madhuri Bite**

www.the-criterion.com

AboutUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/about/>

Archive: <http://www.the-criterion.com/archive/>

ContactUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/contact/>

EditorialBoard: <http://www.the-criterion.com/editorial-board/>

Submission: <http://www.the-criterion.com/submission/>

FAQ: <http://www.the-criterion.com/fa/>

ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Contemporary Relevance and Translation of Ancient Jaina Texts: A Study of Ācārya Amitgati's *Subhāṣita-Ratna-Saṃdoha*

Kriti Jain

Research Scholar,
Department of English and Modern European Languages,
Banasthali Vidyapith.

Geetha Yadav

Associate Professor,
Banasthali Vidyapith.

Article History: Submitted-31/07/2025, Revised-14/08/2025, Accepted-19/08/2025, Published-31/08/2025.

Abstract:

Translation Studies as an academic domain systematically deals with translations as a vast arena and has been providing wider readership to literatures earlier confined within the circumference of their source language and culture; hence significantly shaping the literary canon, making it more inclusive, democratic and enriched. Unlike prominent ancient texts, which are vigorously translated and read, there is a plethora of ancient Jain religious texts that remain untouched by the benefits of translations. This paper is an attempt to bring into light a comparatively lesser-known eleventh century work, *Subhāṣita-Ratna-Saṃdoha*, written by Ācārya Amitgati that holds immense wealth for present readers worldwide. The paper asserts the need for English translations of this text by establishing its contemporary relevance. It sheds light on the social, psychological, religious and spiritual elements, and the universality of themes around which it revolves making the need of this text in the contemporary world evident.

Keywords: Translation Studies, Jain Literature, Ācārya Amitgati, *Subhāṣita-Ratna-Saṃdoha*.

Introduction: Jaina Literature in the Ancient Indian Literary Canon

The ancient Jain traditional knowledge system is an all-encompassing arena that entails treasures which if tapped rightly are a boon to the 21st century contemporary society. The plethora of knowledge that it entails has come down from centuries of experimentation, observation and transmission through oral means as well as written canon. It spans over vast fields including philosophy, literature, cosmology, science, medicine, politics, economics, psychology and sociology and has the potential to sustainably support the modern global scenario through its wealth of wisdom. This knowledge is laid on firm foundations and is time-tested and can act as a remedy to a lot of contemporary problems.

Literature of a nation is woven from the social, cultural, political and economic threads that have existed in it. "Jainism is one of the oldest religions in India. It evolved in an early period of Indian history. It is a religion with a complete system; it has its dogma, metaphysics, philosophy, mythology, ethics and rituals. It is a living religion" (Sharma 1).

Jaina literature spans over a significant portion of the entire Indian traditional literary canon. Prem Chand Jain in his essay "The Jaina Contribution to the History of Ancient India" talks about the authenticity of the sources and expresses the importance of the Hindu, Buddhist and Jaina community texts as an important source of ancient historical information apart from archaeology, epigraphy, numismatics and foreigners' accounts. He claims, "Jaina sources are remarkable for their variety, vastness and chronological sequence. They are spread over the whole range of historical times and are connected with practically every part of the country and with almost every phase of its history" (Jain 41). However, he says that Jaina texts are not that much explored compared to Buddhist and Hindu texts and the works explored show promising results regarding their reliability and their possibility of becoming impressive sources that mirror ancient Indian society. Therefore, it is necessary that these texts must be studied and

explored by scholars and translated in better numbers so that they could become available to scholars and researchers across the globe, without much language barriers.

In his *The Jainas in History of Indian Literature*, the author, Dr Maurice Winternitz, gives a survey of the Jaina literature in Indian history, its characteristics, genres, connection with other literatures and scope including the narrative literature, poetic literature, lyrical and didactic poetry, scientific and technical literature and literature related to politics. Winternitz employees the term "Ascetic Literature" which he characterizes as- its disregard for caste system, its heroes being kings or merchants or śūdras and not just gods or saints, the stories being taken from popular tales, fairy stories, fables and parables, and insists on the sufferings of samsara and teaches morality and compassion and ahimsa (4). To quote Winternitz, "In the sacred texts of Jainas, a great part of Ascetic Literature of ancient India is embodied which has also left its traces in Buddhist literature as well as the Epics and *Purāṇas*."(9). Hence, it is observed that Jaina literature is a storehouse of literary genres and styles, is interdisciplinary, and has a give-and-take relationship with other contemporary religious literatures.

The literary canon of the Jainas is enormously multifaceted and entails various fields which are divided into various genres. As explained in *Mokṣamārgaprakāśaka* by Pt. Todarmal Ji, Jaina literature is broadly divided into four genres or 'Ānuyogas', namely *Prathamānuyoga*, *Caraṇānuyoga*, *Karṇānuyoga* and *Dravyānuyoga*. *Prathamānuyoga* comprises of stories of 63 Shalaka purushas including kings, monks, eminent religious personalities, art, literature, poetry and history. Major works include Raviṣeṇa's *Padma Purāṇa*, Jinasena's *Harivaṃśapurāṇa*, etc. *Caraṇānuyoga* contains texts that deal with proper conduct, principles of observance, behaviour according to Jīva's *guṇasthāna* and similar literature. Examples include Samantabhadra's *Ratnkaranda Śrāvākācāraa* and Vaṭṭakera's *Mūlācāra*. *Karṇānuyoga* deals with the description of the universe and entails geography, mathematics, astronomy, astrology and the philosophy of Karma and similar literature. Prominent examples include Vīrasena's

Jayadhavalā Ṭīkā and Nemicandra's *Gommaṭasāra*. *Dravyānuyoga* focuses on the philosophical doctrines, theories and *tattvajñāna*, basically about the dichotomy between the soul and the other. Significant works include Kundakunda's *Samayasāra* and *Pravacanasāra*. A study of these genres reveals how each of them contain themes which are of great help to contemporary global audience.

Jain Texts and the Tradition of Multilingualism and Translations

In the building of the Jain literary canon, translations have been a dynamic and multifaceted tradition. This tradition has evolved through and spans over various phases, including oral transmission, vernacularisation, Sanskritization and modern linguistic adaptations. Jaina translators and scholars have been committed to accessibility, philosophical clarity and linguistic innovation, hence shaping the literary landscape of India. This practice has ensured the transmission and preservation of the legacy of Jain texts and wisdom across cultures and centuries.

The Introduction to *Literary Transcreation as a Jain Practice* discusses the contribution of the Jains in the following way, “The Jains have contributed particularly in three significant ways that could all be interpreted as signalling a concern for preservation and transmission: the first is the production and preservation of manuscripts, the second is the creation of adaptations and translations, and the third is the privileging of multilingualism” (Jonckheere 11). Hence, these three factors, including a practice to preserve manuscripts, propagation of adaptations and an exploration of multilingualism, together contribute in the production of Jaina texts. The origin and evolution of Jain texts and their translations is studied as follows.

Initially, Jainism originated as a practice of passing down of knowledge verbally from the teachings of Tīrthaṅkaras, Gaṇadhara (immediate disciple of Tīrthaṅkaras) and subsequent monks known as the Śruta-paramparā. This uninterrupted transmission or passing down of

knowledge depended on direct transfer, spiritual insight and memorising power. Tirthankaras preached in *Samavsharana*, which was meticulously preserved and propagated as Shrut Jnana, and further transmitted by Shrut Kevalis or senior monks. For centuries, this oral tradition ensured the continuity and fidelity of the Shrut Jnana.

Then, until few years after the nirvāṇa of Mahāvīra, the Śruta-paramparā continued to exist through oral preachings and earnings majorly by monks and scholars. It lasted till Ācārya Dhārṣeṇa in the first century CE, under whose influence the indoctrination of the scriptures began. Anticipating the diminishment of Shrut Jnana or loss of oral knowledge, Ācārya Dhārṣeṇa passed down his knowledge to his disciples Puṣpadanta and Bhūtabali and instructed them to write it down in order to preserve the available knowledge. In this way, a shift occurred from oral to written tradition, which resulted in the documentation of the first Jaina text *Ṣaṭkhaṇḍāgama*. This day is celebrated as Śruta Pañcamī. Subsequently, the Jain Canonical literature gradually got organised into structured books documenting the eleven aṅgas and fourteen pūrvas that Shrut Jnana comprised, and hence the shaping of written scriptures took place. The Jaina scriptures were formulated in Ardhamāgadhī Prakrit, a middle Indo-Aryan language, and were preserved by generations of saints and scholars who transmitted them down. With the geographical and temporal spread of Jainism, the incorporation of additional languages like Sanskrit, Gujarati, Tamil etc became evident.

Linguistic expansion as an attribute of the written canon is invoked here. The recording was done in Prakrit, particularly Ardhamāgadhī and Śaurasenī, reflecting the vernacular prevalent during that time in that region. However, in 5th century CE, a linguistic turn took place where Sanskritization of the texts was adopted. Among the intellectual elites, Sanskrit occupied a place of repute and was widely circulated across the subcontinent. A scholarly observation notes that, "The Jaina researchers understood that the Sanskrit language had a more extensive reach and could help in proliferating the lessons of the Jaina religion to a bigger crowd" ("Jaina

literature in Sanskrit"). It is important to emphasize the fact that the introduction of Sanskritization did not come with an abandonment of Prakrit, in fact, both the languages complemented each other in the textual tradition. This enabled the scholars to have a wider participation in the intellectual discourse.

Linguistic evolution and promotion of vernaculars took place in order to make the teachings accessible and comprehensible to a broader audience, across cultures. Extensive commentaries and sub commentaries were written and circulated to supplement the Dvādaśāṅga (twelve aṅgas). The Jain Literature was translated as well as composed in various languages including Saṃskṛta, Maharāṣṭrī Prākṛta, Śaurasenī, Tamiḷ, Kannaḍa, Marāṭhī, Rājasthānī, Dhundari, Mārwārī, Hindī, Gujarātī, Malayāḷam, and, foreign languages like English and German. Acharya Hemchandra, for instance, wrote the *Siddha-Hema-Śabdānuśāśana*, a comprehensive grammar covering Sanskrit, Prakrit, and Apabhramsha, which had a significant impact on the development of Gujarati and other regional languages. Jain grammarians played a pivotal role in the codification and standardisation of Indian languages, both Dravidian and Indo-Aryan. Jain monks in southern India wrote extensively in Tamil during the Sangam period, hence contributing to the foundational Tamil grammar and literary texts. The *Tolkāppiyam*, the oldest available Tamil grammar, is attributed to a Jain author, and later grammar works like *Nannūḷ* were also composed by Jain ascetics ("Jain Literature"). The introduction of *Transcreation as a Jaina Practice* notes how Jain authors wrote extensively in various Middle Indic languages (including Prakrit and Apabhramsha), besides Sanskrit, and "were the first to start writing in vernacular languages, the extent of which one author in this volume has called 'a major chapter in the global history of translation'" (Jonckheere 12).

Jain authors were one of the pioneers who formulated religious, spiritual and philosophical texts in regional languages, making texts on spirituality more accessible and democratic for the ordinary people. The Jain community practiced Svādhyāya or self-study or study of the Self,

for which they installed huge libraries or *bhaṇḍāras* inside their temples, wherein some of the largest collections of manuscripts were preserved. Such activities cultivated intellectualism and cultural production, which became a fertile ground for translations, transcreations and adaptations. In *Introduction: Jain Transcreations and the Creativity of Similarity*, it is evident that “another result of the intellectualism Jains cultivated for themselves was the translation and transcreation of many works of poetry, philosophy, grammar, astrology, and political and other sciences, besides religious and didactic texts. While the influence of the Jain belief system is visible in many of these texts, it is important to point out that Jains as a community organised by means of their religious affiliation contributed to all genres of Indian literature” (Jonkheere 12).

The contribution of Jain scholars to translation, grammar, and literature has been widely acknowledged. As German scholar Georg Bühler observed, “In grammar, in astronomy as well as in all branches, the achievements of the Jains have been so great that even their opponents have taken notice of them and that some of their works are of importance for European science even today. In the south, where they have worked among the Dravidian peoples, they have also promoted the development of these languages. The Kanarese, Tamil, Telugu literary languages rest on the foundations erected by the Jain monks” (Sen 74).

Characteristics and Contemporary Relevance of Jaina Literature

The relevance of traditional Jain wisdom in modern society can be explored through some of its characteristics. Firstly, the ancient Jaina knowledge system is universal in its themes and appeal. It explores human concerns like the nature of truth, reality, the meaning and purpose of life, and the pursuit of happiness. Its timeless wisdom appeals to the population across cultures and generations. Secondly, it is based on very strong ethical foundations that explore the dilemmas and problems that human beings go through, and offers guidance, justice and helps

them navigate through life. The principles it is based on primarily involve truthfulness, non-violence, dutifulness etc., which are much needed in every society irrespective of the time-period. Thirdly, the traditional knowledge system is very holistic in its approach. This implies that it does not only deal with physical well-being, but also delves into the depths of mental, emotional and spiritual well-being of an individual. This holistic approach makes it very relevant in the 21st century because it makes the individuals introspective, guides them and makes them capable enough to deal with the crisis that one encounters in day-to-day lives. Fourth, its scientific and practical approaches need to be looked up to by modern scholars. Time and again, it has been proven that the treasure of ancient Indian canon is very scientific and practical, especially when it comes to mathematics, astrology, medicine etc. Also, it is very sustainable and in accordance with nature and human society. Its means are such that they would sustain for longer lengths of time as compared to the modern ways of utilizing resources that end up depleting them. Lastly, the literary and cultural value that it upholds is of utmost importance. Mythology and folklore bring down traditional wisdom through artistic ways and hence help in the preservation of culture. Lal argues that the strength of Indian literature lies in its myth content, because myth “impregnates literature not only with literary value but moral and religious value as well” (Lal 2).

It inspires artistic expression and deliberation on profound issues through dialogues presented creatively, so that they become fascinating and comprehensible to humanity in general. Also, the study of ancient languages like Sanskrit, Prakrit and Pali connects one with the humongous literary wealth of the nation, and helps in inspiring feelings of pride in ones' national identity.

Jaina literary canon is diverse, and in order to examine its contemporary relevance, its characteristics and pillar principles must be pondered upon. First, it is based on ethical principles that are timeless and universal. The vow of *Ahimsā* actively propagates the idea of

non-violence against any living being- not just through actions but also through words or thoughts. It encompasses all living beings and thus, could cure present world that is grappling with issues of animal cruelty, environmental degradation, and armed conflicts. *Aparigraha* means non-possession and mindful consumption of resources and refraining from hoarding materials more than what is needed. It could cure the problems of sustainability and can bring in ethical consumerism. *Anekāntavāda* emphasizes on the multifaceted nature of reality and promotes tolerance, understanding, and open-mindedness in navigating diverse perspectives and complex situations. Second, Jaina literature explores psychological well-being and mindfulness. Its philosophy of karma and the birth-death-rebirth cycle invokes introspectiveness and self-reflection in humans. Its unique practices of meditation and search for the 'self' have gained widespread recognition and are beneficial in managing stress, improving focus, and enhancing emotional well-being. Third, Jaina literature is scientific and practical. It includes Mathematics to which the Jaina mathematicians have made significant contributions (for example, the number theory which has had a profound impact on mathematics and science); Astronomy to which the Jain astronomical texts have revealed sophisticated observations of the celestial bodies, offering valuable insights for contemporary astronomy and understanding the universe; and, Logic to which Jain texts have contributed a rigorous system that emphasizes on truth and non-contradiction, and can be applied to critical thinking and problem-solving in various fields. Lastly, the social, economic, environmental, political, and literary insights that Jaina literary canon has, holds immense value for the contemporary audience, and is truly a treasure if its potential is tapped in the appropriate ways. In *A History of Jaina Literature*, Dr Winternitz observes, "The Jains have extended their activities beyond the sphere of their own religious literature to a far greater extent than the Buddhists have done, and they have memorable achievements in the secular sciences to their

credit, in philosophy, grammar, lexicography, poetics, mathematics, astronomy and astrology, and even in the science of politics (Winternitz 313).

Ācārya Amitagati II and His *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha*

Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha is a verse collection of 922 verses written in the tenth century AD in the Sanskrit language by Ācārya Amitagati II. The work is of immense value and needs to be translated, circulated, and promoted in the contemporary world. It is valuable not only for the scholars and researchers but also the ordinary folks because of its diverse content and universal appeal.

Ācārya Amitagati- II is one of the most prominent saints in the Jaina lineage of saints and writers. He was a saint of the Mathur Sanga. The time-period of the author is mentioned in some of his works, including *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha*, *Dharmāparīkṣā* and *Pañcasamgraha*. From the account of Indian Historian Vishweshwarnath Reu, in his *Bhārata Ke Prācīna Rājavamśa- Bhag I* (1920), it can be deduced that Ācārya Amitagati created *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha* in Vikram Samvat 1050, i.e., 993 AD and *Dharmāparīkṣā* in Vikram Samvat 1070, i.e., 1013 AD, during the reign of King Munj. (Reu 101) Hence, Ācārya Amitagati's time period can be traced to the tenth and eleventh centuries AD. He is best known for his works *Dharmāparīkṣā* and *Bhāvanādvātriṃśatikā*; while the other works that are undoubtedly authored by him include *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha*, *Amitagati Śrāvākācāra*, *Upāsakācāra*, *Pañcasamgraha*, *Ārādhanā Saṃgraha*, *Candraprajñapti*, *Sārdhadvayaprajñapti*, *Vyākhyāprajñapti* and *Jambūdvīpaprajñapti*.

Dr Maurice Winternitz, in his *The Jainas in History of Indian Literature*, elaborately gives the contribution of the Jaina literature, with its various genres, in the history of Indian literary tradition. He talks about the representation of didactic poetry in the Jaina literary canon, and amidst the various examples that he quotes, he refers to Ācārya Amitagati's poetic works and

writes, "Well known are the didactic poems of Amitagati. He wrote his *Subhāṣita Ratna Samdoha* in 994A.D, a work of great importance for our knowledge of Jaina ethics, and 20 years later in 1014A.D, the *Dharmāparīkṣā* which contains not only moral maxims but also a great number of interesting and amusing stories" (19).

Pandit Kailash Chandra Shastri, in "Preface" to *Subhāṣita Ratna Samdoha*, asserts that Ācārya Amitagati was an efficient writer and had exceptional command over Sanskrit language. His prowess as a poet was unprecedented. His simple and honest writing style can clearly be experienced through his available works. On experiencing his enriched, heart-warming, easy and impassioned poetry collection, heart gets over flooded with joy. As he was the principal of the Mathur sangha, his works are mainly didactic. He has warned human beings of the malpractices and has inspired them to embrace good deeds" (Shastri 6).

Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha: Need of English Translation in the Contemporary Era

First, *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha*'s historical and cultural significance can be observed as the author is considered to be authentic and recognised by several historians and scholars. Pt. Kailash Chandra Shastri mentions Dr A.N. Upadhye in "Preface" to *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha*, according to whom Ācārya Amitagati's name and works were included in booklists published by scholars such as Lumen, Weber, Peterson, Bhandarkar between the years 1886 to 1903. (Shastri 6) Ācārya Amitagati mentions the time-period of his texts in various works, which helps the scholars allocate him chronologically. Also, he mentions the kingdom and the king under whose reign he wrote "when one thousand and fifty years had passed to the death of King Vikarm, and King Munj was ruling the land" the book was written (Jaina 289). He gives reference of his *Guru-paramparā* as well which becomes significant when it comes to the historical study of the text, both in terms of Indian history as well as Jaina religious history. Moreover, intertextuality can be observed in his works where the author has borrowed from his

predecessors and contemporaries, and the later writers seem to have been inspired from his works. An example can be Ācārya Hemacandra's (d.1229 A.D.) *Yogaśāstra*, which is influenced by Ācārya Amitagati's *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha* and *Śrāvakācāra* that talks about the broader nature of Yoga, the pious behaviour of the saints, of which meditation is just a part. Lastly, *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha* uses examples and instances that could be used as a mirror to study his contemporary society. Hence, it can become a lens through which ancient Indian culture, values and practices could be viewed.

Second, the literary value of the book can be evaluated through a study of the writing style, literary devices, language and content. *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha* is written in poetic form and has 922 verses which are beautifully woven together, and add to the immense wealth of *Subhāṣita Saṃdohas* that exist in Sanskrit literature- Bhartṛhari's *Nītiśataka*, *Śṛṅgāraśataka* and *Vairāgyaśataka*, and particularly in Jaina literature, Guṇabhadra's *Ātmānuśāsana*. It is written in several *chandas*, some of which include Anuṣṭup and Śikhariṇī, and is predominated by Śāntarasa because its content instils *vairāgya* or mortification. It is filled with similes and metaphors, for instance in the text, Ācārya very beautifully writes about his motive behind writing this text in the opening verse and says-just like the rays of the sun end darkness to brighten up everything and make the lotuses grow, similarly these *Subhāṣitas* will do away with the darkness of ignorance regarding the living and the non-living and they will make the hearts of the readers filled with joy (Jaina 1).

Moreover, the writing style of Ācārya Amitagati is very clear and simple, and such that it could be understood by everyone. He, being the leader of the Mathur Sangha, has a didactic bent to his writing, but what makes him stand apart is his style of amalgamating principles and examples. This style makes his philosophy and the knowledge that he wants to impart very clear to his readers. Also, like a dexterous artist and reader of human mind that he comes out to be through his works, he raises questions that he thinks would come to the minds of the

readers, and then answers them tactfully. Due to his diplomacy, the book is filled with questions and solutions that are general to humankind, and hence becomes a text that imparts essential lessons.

Third, the psychological and emotional value of the text must also be evaluated. It deals with human emotions like anger, greed and lust, and through comparisons and analogies, the writer explains how they are hazardous to one's peace of mind. Issues of pain and deep grief and extreme indulgence in pleasures of senses leads to ill decision making by humans, and prevents them from experiencing the joyous nature of the soul. For instance, he writes, "intoxication of any one of the senses also makes the living beings lose their lives, then what to say about those who are vehement in the material pleasures of all five sense organs? They will definitely get destroyed, that is why rational men never get controlled by the materials of sense organs and keep on renouncing them" (Jaina 31). Hence, this text can cater to the needs of understanding human nature, trauma management, anger management and stress management pertaining to excessive desire for materialistic pleasures.

Fourth, the religious and philosophical significance of the text lies in the fact that it is written by an eminent saint who was the principal of an entire sangha. His prowess as a scholar of a diverse range of topics is evident through the mass of his available works. *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha* is predominantly a text of *Caraṇānuyoga* which implies that it deals with the right/proper conduct and behaviour by shravakas or householders. It has a blend of *Karṇānuyoga* and *Dravyānuyoga* as well, which implies that it contains the philosophy of karma and destiny, and the nature of the soul and the means to experience its complete purity, respectively. Moreover, it sheds light on the topics such as, the nature of knowledge, guru, religion, pain, death, transience of materials etc in great detail, with examples and instances from everyday human lives.

Fifth, the environmentalist point of view can also be examined while looking at the contemporary relevance of the text. *Ahimsā*, *Aparigraha*, abstinence from honey, meat and alcohol consumption, and the ideal conduct for householders that is described in the text, could greatly uplift the 21st-century society. The vow of *Ahimsā* actively propagates the idea of *Ahimsā*, which entails non-violence against any living being- not just through actions but also through words or thoughts. In *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha*, shloka 213, the author summarizes the classification of *Jīvas* varying from organisms of single sensory organ to organisms of five-sensory organs, in accordance with the Jaina literary canon. He writes that, “all worldly living beings come under the five categories of living organisms and not making them suffer through one’s thoughts, words or actions is the vow of *Ahimsā*” (75). Hence, it is evident that not harming the environment and the society on the whole is very intrinsic to the Jaina philosophy and way of life. *Aparigraha* means non-possession. It is a restraint from one’s own greed, avarice and the habit of hoarding more than what is required for sustenance. It requires to keep in check or give up all such pleasures that come by harming, hurting or killing other living organisms according to one’s stage in life (*Jīva’s guṇasthāna*). This Jain vow is the principle of limiting one’s possessions (*parimita-parigraha*) and limiting one’s desires (*iccha-parimana*). Ācārya dedicates an entire chapter to the sermon to restrain from greed, wherein he explains the demerits of greed and hoarding through several metaphors and asserts on giving it up. While looking at it through the frame of environmentalism, this is a pivotal principle as all the activities that cause the destruction of environment, have human greed as their root cause.

Lastly, personal and social upliftment could also be brought about through the understanding and application of this text, as it makes individuals understand oneself as well as the society better. Practices such as illicit sexual affairs, alcohol, honey and meat consumption, and too much indulgence in pleasures of senses drive humans into wrong judgements and malpractices,

those disturb the functioning of the society and lead to crimes and infringe peace. In *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṁdoha*, shloka 53-594 in the discussion on lust, author encourages to give up upon lust and illicit sexual desires where he writes, “as much harm as is caused to a human by lust cannot be caused even by a vengeful ruler, lion, elephant, snake or poison... therefore rational humans try to control enemy-like-lust at the soonest” (198). There are three independent chapters dedicated to abstinence from alcohol, meat and honey consumption. Discussing abstinence from alcohol consumption, shloka 507 mentions the infinite number of micro-organisms that reside in it, and shloka 508 mentions the physical, and psychological ill effects of alcohol consumption and how it leads humans to take reckless actions, which are hazardous to their surroundings. The chapter pertaining to abstinence from Meat consumption, in shloka 533 defines that meat is the body of organisms with 2-5 sense organs and not of the ones with single sense organ. Shloka 530 sheds light on how vegetarianism is better than consuming animal-based food because of the stark difference in the number of organisms residing in both their bodies. Shloka 535 mentions the physical impacts of non-vegetarianism and how it causes lethargy, lust and induces greed and reckless behaviour. Next, abstinence from consumption of Honey is discussed in the following chapter, wherein in shloka 550 and 552 acharya mentions how honey is obtained through killing of numerous organisms, has several organisms living in it and procuring it is a cruel process, as the secretion collected by bees through hard labour is snatched away unjustly by humans. In shloka 560 and 562, acharya insists on giving up of the usage of honey by oneself, helping others in its production or utilization or appreciating others over its usage, as any of these three acts promotes the production of honey and leads to miserable death of innumerable organisms. Also, Ācārya talks about *śrāvakā* dharma or the conduct of the householder, that should be practised in order to lead an enriched life, which in turn leads to a well-functioning society.

Hence, *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha* is a comparatively lesser-known text by Ācārya Amitgati whose value has not yet been explored and acknowledged. Hence, there is a need to translate it into English language so that it becomes accessible to scholars as well as common people without any language barrier.

Conclusion

Taking a glimpse of the entire tapestry of Jain literature and its tradition of translations, it is deduced that its humongous canon is filled with wealth, that if wisely utilized, can prove to be a boon for the 21st-century society. Jaina literature, that forms a major portion of it, is spread over a wide range of themes that can act as a cure to contemporary global problems- social, political, economic, psychological, environmental, legal and so on. Particularly, *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha* as a representative text of the traditional Jain literary canon is proved to be a treasure for the contemporary society and the universal knowledge that it contains, if critically examined, understood and applied could help humanity navigate through much of the contemporary global issues as a society as well as personally.

Works Cited:

“A History of Jaina Literature.” vol. 2, Calcutta, 1933, pp. 594-95. *Studies in Jain Literature*, p. 313, https://jainqq.org/booktext/Education_in_Jainism/269156.

De Clercq, Eva, Heleen De Jonckheere, and Simon Winant, editors. *Literary Transcreation as a Jain Practice*. Ergon Verlag, 2025. DOI: 10.5771/9783987401602. Accessed 4 Feb. 2025.

“Jaina literature in Sanskrit.” Studocu, Alagappa University, <https://www.studocu.com/in/document/alagappa-university/socio-cultural-history-of-tamil-nadu-from-1800-to-1967-ce/jaina-literature-in-sanskrit/53857754>. Accessed 31 July 2025.

“Jain literature.” Wikipedia, Wikimedia Foundation, 31 July 2025, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jain_literature. Accessed 31 July 2025.

Jain, Prem Chand. “The Jaina Contribution to History of Ancient India.” *Jaina Journal: A Quarterly on Jainology*, vol. 17, Jaina Bhawan Publication, 1982.

Jaina, Shrilal. *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha*. Central Sanskrit University, 2010.

Lal, Purushottama. *Great Sanskrit Plays in New English Transcreations*. New Directions, 1957.

Reu, Vishveshwar Nath. *Bhārata Ke Prācīna Rājavaṃśa*. Vol. 1, Hindi Granth Ratnakar Karyalaya, 1920.

Sanjay Shastri Jevar. “Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha.” YouTube, 2020, https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLbSIIVJNaOtFGkJBdKByOo_6Fq20vUvLr.

Sen, Sailendra Nath. *Ancient Indian History and Civilization*. New Age International, 1999, p. 74. ISBN: 978-81-224-1198-0.

Sharma, V. K. *History of Jainism: With Special Reference to Mathura*. DK Printworld Pvt. Ltd., 2002, p. 1.

Shastri, Balchandra. *Subhāṣita Ratna Saṃdoha*. Jivraj Granthmala, 2006.

Shastri, Nemichandra. *Tīrthaṃkara Bhagavāna Mahāvīra Aura Unakī Ācārya Paramparā*, vol. 2, Ācārya Shantisagar Chhani Granthmala.

Todarmal. *Mokṣamārgaprakāśaka*. No. 29, Pandit Todarmal Smarak Trust, 2011.

Winternitz, Maurice. *The Jainas in the History of Indian Literature*. Revised by Jina Vijaya Muni, Jaina Sahitya Samsodhan Pratisthan, 1946.

Winternitz, Maurice. *A History of Indian Literature*. Vol. 2, *Buddhist and Jaina Literature*, translated by S. Ketkar and H. Kohn, revised by the author, Calcutta University Press, 1933.